

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPE OBJECTS FOR SOCIO-TECHNICAL SYSTEM VISUALIZATION

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Introduction

The study of agricultural landscapes reveals multifold interactions among human activities, technologies, and the environment. These interactions design landscape objects that serve as spatial manifestations of agricultural socio-technical systems. According to Geel (2004), a sociotechnical system is a set of interconnected, heterogeneous elements, such as resources, artefacts, knowledge, actors and institutions, that fulfil a specific societal function, such as food production. Landscape objects, as Antrop (2005) suggests, are spatially discernible elements resulting from a combination of natural processes and human activities, reflecting farming practices, management choices, and technological developments (Sklenicka et al., 2009). Examples include cultivated fields, livestock facilities, and runoff management structures. Deffontaines (2004) refined the definition drawing upon farmers' views on these objects, making explicit the role of farming practices in their ontology and establishing them as tools for visualizing complex socio-technical interactions in agricultural landscapes. However, most studies on agricultural landscape dynamics leave the definition of these objects implicit. This review explores how spatial objects are defined and used within scientific literature for visualizing socio-technical systems, aiming to improve understanding and modelling of farming systems. By 'visualization', we refer specifically to the spatial representation of interactions that shape these systems.

Methods

We conducted a scoping review to examine how the term "object" relates to agricultural socio-technical systems in scientific literature. Initially, we tested search queries in Google Scholar combining terms like "objects" and "agricultural landscape" or "agricultural space"—and the French equivalent terms—to gain a topic overview and refine keywords. Then, we searched Web of Science "Core collections" (all editions) retrieving 1066 documents (1988–2025) on March 6, 2025, using the query "Object" and "Agricultural landscape". We screened this literature body to keep studies that: (i) explicitly deal with landscape objects in agricultural contexts, (ii) address landscapes' socio-technical dimensions by examining how social practices and spatial objects mutually shape each other through stakeholder engagement, knowledge integration, or policy analysis, and (iii) discuss methods for visualizing socio-technical systems. Studies focusing solely on biophysical aspects without considering social factors, were excluded. Sixty-two studies were selected for an inductive, iterative analysis of the full texts, which allowed us to identify how landscape objects are defined and used.

Results

The Role of Landscape Objects in Visualizing Socio-Technical Systems

The early results of the literature review reveal four main roles of landscape objects in visualizing socio-technical systems (Figure 1), illustrated below through selected examples.

- *Interfaces between technical and social systems.* Dimopoulos and Kizos (2020) used object-oriented image analysis to integrate historical events and land use changes, interpreted through stakeholder insights, enhancing understanding of local adaptations to external pressures. Tarolli et al. (2014) interpret a specific object, terraces, as visible evidence of the dynamic interaction between human needs and the environmental management techniques developed by local communities.
- *Spatialization of changes and processes.* For instance, Marignani et al. (2008) employed landscape objects in retrospective data analysis to compare past ecosystem configurations, to address historical land-use changes integrating information on ecological, spatial, and temporal issues.
- *Support for ecosystem services.* Steingröver et al. (2010) demonstrate how green-blue networks serve as spatial objects linking conservation and landscape development, and how stakeholders use them to inform multifunctional landscape management strategies.
- *Mediation between perceptions and biophysical reality.* Zhou et al. (2023) focus on agricultural terraces to develop a matrix combining objective visual sensitivity data with subjective aesthetic preferences, to prioritize landscape improvement areas.

Figure 1. Landscape objects' roles in visualizing socio-technical systems and landscape dynamics.

Discussion and Perspectives

This work explores how agricultural landscape objects facilitate the visualization of socio-technical systems. We identified four main roles ranging from static descriptions, such as interfaces, and supports for spatializations of change or ecosystem services, to dynamic mediation of different perceptions. The review could be expanded to include alternative keywording of “object” such as relevant adjectives (e.g., intermediary, boundary, transactional) or study-specific terms (e.g., structures, components). A systematic semantic comparison of how research addresses these objects would further enhance our understanding of the interplay between visible landscape features and invisible farming practices. Such insights would inform the development of an agent-based model that simulates the influence of intermediate actors and policies on crop choice configurations.

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